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Deliverable 1.1

Stakeholder engagement strategy

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Executive Summary

The aim of the ARCFISH project is to develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), supporting sustainable fisheries in the Arctic. The DTO will be based on the existing Blue Insight platform that seamlessly supports the market segments of the ocean observing value chain of the New Blue Economy (Heslop et al., 2022). The New Blue Economy, also known as the Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE), is a concept that promotes sustainable development and conservation of ocean resources for economic, social, and environmental benefits. In the Arctic, sustainable fisheries focusing on achieving long-term sustainability and resilience of ocean ecosystems and communities is the key to uphold good living conditions for its residents. The project will target two key regions for Arctic fisheries: (1) Western Greenland, centred around Disko Bay, and (2) region around Iceland, northwards to the Svalbard archipelago and the Barents Sea.

To have proper impact and exploitable project results, it will be essential to work closely with a variety of stakeholders in the development phase of co-creating an Arctic Fisheries DTO. This includes, among others; fishers, seafood processors, researchers, authorities, regulatory bodies, policy-and decision-makers.

The project will encourage stakeholder's involvement throughout the development process of the ARCFISH DTO, facilitating regular feedback and collaboration to ensure that the final product aligns with the end-user's expectations. It is important to avoid stakeholder fatigue, so the project partners will identify and prioritize stakeholders based on their area, interest, and expectations. A certain protocol is suggested in this deliverable on how to approach stakeholders and involve them in the project and project workshops. This protocol will be followed to establish and maintain a fruitful dialogue with stakeholders within the targeted regions and the wider Arctic science and fisheries communities.

Contents

Executive Summary.....	3
List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Aims of the Stakeholder engagement strategy.....	7
2.1. Stakeholders	7
2.2. Engagement strategy.....	8
3. Conclusions	10
4. References.....	10

List of Figures

Figure 1. The ocean observing value chain of the New Blue Economy (Heslop et al., 2022).....	6
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List of Tables

Table 1. Candidates for ARCFISH extended Stakeholder Group.....	8
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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
ICES ASC	ICES Annual Scientific Conference
SBE	Sustainable Blue Economy
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership
SW	Software

1. Introduction

The aim of the ARCFISH project is to develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), supporting sustainable fisheries in the Arctic. The DTO will be based on the existing Blue Insight platform that seamlessly supports the market segments of the ocean observing value chain of the New Blue Economy (Heslop et al., 2022). The New Blue Economy, also known as the Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE), is a concept that *promotes sustainable development and conservation of ocean resources for economic, social, and environmental benefits*. In the Arctic, sustainable fisheries focusing on achieving long-term sustainability and resilience of ocean ecosystems and communities is the key to uphold good living conditions for its residents.

However, the negative impacts of traditional economic activities such as overfishing, marine pollution, habitat destruction, and climate change have threatened the health and sustainability of the ocean, leading to declining fish stocks, loss of biodiversity, and increased coastal vulnerability to natural disasters. New data products and services, co-developed with relevant stakeholders, are needed to provide a better basis for decision-making in fisheries planning and management.

Figure 1. The ocean observing value chain of the New Blue Economy (Heslop et al., 2022).

The ARCFISH project has special focus on two key regions for Arctic fisheries: (1) Western Greenland, centred around Disko Bay, and (2) region around Iceland, northwards to the Svalbard archipelago and the Barents Sea. By leveraging the Consortium’s network in these regions and adopting a multi-stakeholder co-creation approach in the development of a DTO tailored for sustainable fisheries in the Arctic, the long term goal is to create new data products and sustainable services for the fisheries community both in the two targeted regions as well as across the Arctic.

ARCFISH project and this deliverable, will address the following research question on how a broad stakeholder community can be mobilised and engaged in co-development of new data products and services providing useful information for sustainable fisheries?

2. Aims of the Stakeholder engagement strategy

For the project to be successful and have an expected impact, it is essential to work closely with a variety of stakeholders (e.g., fishers, seafood processors, researchers, authorities, regulatory bodies, policy-and decision-makers) to co-create an Arctic Fisheries DTO (Digital Twin of the Ocean).

The plan is to have a series of workshops early on in the project, to develop initial requirement specification, identify what data is available, what additional data would be relevant to collect and utilize, identify data and innovation gaps, and initiate further cooperation to actively engage stakeholders in the work towards novel digital solutions and project impact.

A second round of workshops will be held mid-way through the project to alpha test the developed solutions and collect feedback from stakeholders for further development. Towards the end of the project a third round of stakeholder events will be facilitated where the solutions will be beta tested with relevant stakeholders. These events will, when possible, be co-located with events that stakeholders attend e.g. Arctic Circle, Arctic Frontiers, ICES ASC, Nor-Fishing, or relevant events of other projects. Capacity building tailored to the needs of stakeholders will be a central element of workshops and other events organised by work package 1 (WP1) of the ARCFISH project.

ARCFISH is centred around a multi-stakeholder co-creation approach, and one task in WP1 is focused on facilitating a holistic approach to stakeholder engagement. The task will develop a stakeholder involvement strategy and maintain good stakeholder involvement in the project as a whole, making sure all stakeholders are heard whilst avoiding stakeholder fatigue. The final output of the task will be a white paper on the Arctic Fisheries DTO services and applications.

2.1. Stakeholders

As stated in Section 1, the project aims to generate results that support scientists, policy makers and resource users to make better informed decisions. Therefore, it is essential to work closely with a variety of stakeholders (e.g., fishers, seafood processors, researchers, authorities, regulatory bodies, policy-and decision-makers) in the development phase of co-creating an Arctic Fisheries DTO.

The project will encourage stakeholder's involvement throughout the development process of the DTO, facilitate regular feedback and collaboration to ensure that the final product aligns with the end-user's expectations. These stakeholder groups will probably have different needs and views towards the DTO in the development phase – but their view and opinions will be essential in the co-creation process.

It is important to avoid stakeholder fatigue, so the project partners will identify and prioritize stakeholders based on their area, interest, and expectations. This will help the project to focus on the most relevant and critical stakeholders, and thereby maximizing the use of resources in the project. It is important to communicate clearly and consistently with stakeholders throughout the project lifespan. This means having common clear and realistic outcome expectations for each stakeholder group and providing project updates and feedback on progress and development of DTO. The stakeholders should be involved from the early days of the project and involved in project decision-making, planning, and implementation. This means seeking their input, feedback, and suggestions on key aspects of the project.

The consortium has identified a set of major stakeholders for the ARCFISH DTO (Table 1). These will be engaged in an Arctic DTO Stakeholder Group to elicit requirements, challenges, and gaps.

Table 1. Candidates for ARCFISH extended Stakeholder Group.

Area	Stakeholders
Greenland	Greenland Sustainable Fishery Greenland (SFG), Greenland Institute of Natural Resources (GINR), Greenlandic Ministry of Fisheries, Hunting and Agriculture (APNN).
Iceland	Fisheries Iceland, Marine and Freshwater Research Institute (MFRI), The Directorate of Fisheries, Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO), Icelandic Ocean Cluster, Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization (NAFO).
Pan-Arctic	The Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF) biodiversity working group of the Arctic Council.

2.2. Engagement strategy

The plan is to have a series of stakeholder focused workshops early on in the project, with the aim to:

- Develop initial requirement specification for the ARCFISH DTO
 - Rank what is needed the most and would have the biggest impact
- Identify what:
 - data is available that could be utilized further
 - additional data would be relevant to collect and utilize
 - how and by whom
 - data and innovation gaps there are and ways to close those gaps
- Initiate further cooperation to actively engage stakeholders in the work towards novel digital solutions and project impact.
 - Involve them in project decision-making, planning, and implementation of new data products and services
 - Involve selected stakeholders in the designing of the DTO software architecture and development of software modules
 - Facilitate stakeholder software testing and feedback collection during the development phase, to ensure the final product aligns with the end-user’s expectations.

Before the stakeholder workshops, the project partners must identify which stakeholders are most relevant to be invited to the stakeholder workshops, see table 1. There will be several stakeholder focused workshops early in the project, so there might be the option to invite certain stakeholder groups to one meeting and another group to the next meeting, because these different groups will have different needs and views towards the final project outcomes.

After relevant stakeholders have been classified and put into relevant workshop groups, the stakeholders will be approached by the project, preferably by partners that know them or have had a previous work relationship with them. As stakeholders are usually very busy, their involvement must be carefully planned.

The following protocol should be used when stakeholders are approached.

Meeting invitation should be first sent with 3 weeks' notice. The mail should include a short project description, the aim of the workshop and what is expected of involved stakeholders, list of invited stakeholder organisations, and a plan for follow-up after the workshop. The meeting invitation should be resent one week before the meeting to the stakeholders that have not indicated if they will attend the workshop or not. The invited stakeholders should be called few days before the meeting, just to remind them of the meeting, indicate how important their opinion and feedback could be in the co-creating process of the Arctic Fisheries DTO.

The stakeholder workshops must be case study and therefore area related. The areas focused on in this project are Western Greenland, centred around Disko Bay, and the region around Iceland, northwards to the Svalbard archipelago and the Barents Sea. Stakeholders with a vested interest in these areas as well as in the Pan-Arctic region (Table 1) will be invited to project workshops. The relevant stakeholders involved in software (SW) architecture and model development will be selected beforehand by the involved project participants. A stakeholder will of course have the opportunity to accept or decline the offer of participation. If a stakeholder declines the offer, they will be asked to point out other potential or relevant stakeholder with invested interest in the project scope.

Workshops organisers will follow the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) for workshop invitation and registration procedures. This includes, among others, obtaining consent for use of e.g. photographs from all workshop participants, secure storage of all personal data collected, and ensuring participants at any time can request a copy of their personal data and modify this as necessary. The workshop organisers are responsible for handling all personal data for their participants according to the GDPR.

Conduction the first round of stakeholder workshops.

1. Setting the scene;
 - a. short project introduction
 - b. list of what information are currently collected and utilized, by whom
 - c. availability of the information to others
2. Collect feedback on;
 - a. what information are missing,
 - b. is there data available that could be utilized further,
 - c. what additional data would be relevant to collect and utilize,
 - i. how and by whom,
 - ii. are there data and innovation gaps there are and ways to close those gaps.
3. Explain how the project will address the suggestions and needs of the stakeholder and potential usage of the DTO.
 - a. Collect further feedback regarding the project workshop plan and the role of the DTO.
4. End meeting.

A second round of workshops should be held mid-way through the project to alpha test the developed solutions and collect feedback from stakeholders for further development.

The same protocol for inviting stakeholders to the second-round workshops will be used and similar meeting setup implemented. However, these workshops will focus on the alpha test of the developed solutions and involve selected stakeholders in further co-development of data products and data services, software modules and architecture of the ARCFISH DTO. The aim of these workshops is to facilitate stakeholder software testing and feedback collection during the development phase, to ensure the final product aligns with the end-user's expectations.

Towards the end of the project a third round of stakeholder events will be facilitated where the solutions will be beta tested with relevant stakeholders.

These events will, when possible, be co-located with events that stakeholders attend e.g. Arctic Circle, Arctic Frontiers, ICES ASC, Nor-Fishing, or relevant events of other projects. Capacity building tailored to the needs of stakeholders will be a central element of workshops and other events organised by work package 1 (WP1) of the ARCFISH project.

Documentation of stakeholder input

There will be systematic documentation done in every stakeholder workshop by project partners. The results will be collected in a summary report, that will be categorized by themes from each meeting. During the alpha and beta testing, input from stakeholders will be collected by relevant methods. One option is using the GitHub ticketing system. This is an open-source web application that provides developers with better management of user queries and requests for new or enhanced functionality. Mail parsing with Copilot (AI) is another simple option which requires no extra training on the part of the stakeholder.

3. Conclusions

As stated earlier in this report, the ARCFISH project aims to have results that support scientists, policy makers and resource users to make better informed decisions for sustainable Arctic Fisheries. Therefore, it is essential to work closely with a variety of stakeholders (e.g., fishers, seafood processors, researchers, authorities, regulatory bodies, policy-and decision-makers) in the development phase of co-creating an Arctic Fisheries DTO.

The project will encourage stakeholder's involvement throughout the development process of the DTO, facilitate regular feedback and collaboration to ensure that the final product aligns with the end-user's expectations. These stakeholder groups will probably have different needs and views towards the DTO in the development phase – but their view and opinions will be essential in the co-creation process.

It is important to avoid stakeholder fatigue, so the project partners will identify and prioritize stakeholders based on their area, interest, and expectations. Certain protocol is suggested in this deliverable on how to approach stakeholders and involve them in the project and project workshops. This protocol will be followed for all stakeholder workshops organised by the ARCFISH project.

4. References

Heslop et al., 2022. GOOS / MTS / NOAA DIALOGUES WITH INDUSTRY Background paper V1.

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